

THE ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION AND WORK MOTIVATION IN MEDIATED ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON LECTURER'S PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The destination study is to know the influence direct and not direct culture organization to Culture organization through Satisfaction and Motivation Study this uses analysis quantitative with amount sample of as many as 250 respondents from private universities in Medan City determined using Non-Probability Sampling (Sugiono 2015:84). Data analysis used is a Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. Research results show that cultural organization takes an effect direct positive and significantly to satisfaction work and motivation in work. Then satisfaction work and motivation work take effect direct positive on lecturer performance. Kindly no direct variable Satisfaction work and motivation work capable mediate Culture organization on lecturer performance Private Higher Education in the city of Medan

Keywords: Culture Organization, Satisfaction Work, Motivation work, lecturer performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Lecturer performance in something college tall no can look at light remember from performance here it is wrong one forerunner would student can educated so they can reach by government programs and goals student that alone for draw science by opinion Simanjuntak (2005: 1) which state that, performance lecturer is behavior real displayed _ a lecturer as performance the resulting work in accordance role as power functional academic. interpret performance is level achievement results or implementation Duty certain...to support performance lecturer this must be together with high motivation _ my opinion

Hasibuan in (Sutrisno, 2017) "Finding that motivation is stimulant desire and power mover will work somebody because every motive has destination specific want _ achieved ". for motivation that directed no escape from Culture conclusive organization in college _ tall that in accordance listen to opinion Kreitner and Kinicki in Zuki (2016:33) says " culture Organization is something exists assumptions that are owned, accepted in a manner implicit by the group and determine how to group the feel, think, and react to diverse environment _ variety".

In North Sumatra, there is Type College tall Private as below _ this

Source: LLDIKTI region I, North Sumatra.

Jenis Perguruan Tinggi Swasta	Banyaknya PTS	Mahasiswa	Dosen	
			Tetap	Tidak Tetap
1. Universitas	36	161 673	5 636	987
2. Sekolah Tinggi	102	64 340	2 384	963
3. Institut	9	25 730	726	189
4. Akademi	104	14 164	1 223	536
5. Politeknik	16	4 511	562	82
Jumlah	267	270 418	10 531	2 757

Sumber : LLDIKTI Wilayah-I, Sumatera Utara

List of Universities in the city of Medan

- Darma Agung University , Medan City
- Medan Area University, Medan City
- Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra, Medan City
- Sari Mutiara University of Indonesia, Medan City
- Indonesian Methodist University, Medan City
- Catholic University of Saint Thomas, Medan City
- Panca Budi Development University, Medan City
- Prima University of Indonesia, Medan City
- HKBP Nommensen University, Medan City
- North Sumatra Islamic University, Medan City

College tall private is part of the system education national because those needs keep going encouraged to try to strengthen the ability ranks of the academic community to become more professional and capable following development times so quality. Where Higher Education is determined by accountability and ability to do the Tri Dharma of Higher Education.

By opinion expressed _ by Anggraeni (2013) reveals that the lecturer is required to implement Tri Dharma Higher Education, which activities study be dealt with continuing with publication creation scientifically done _ internally as well in a manner external to use increase performance Lecturer. However in operating Thing the need lecturer who has performance that

good Thing by what Simanjuntak (2005: 1) stated that a performance lecturer is **a behavior real displayed _ by a lecturer as performing the resulting work in accordance role as power functional academic.**

Interpret performance is level achievement results or implementation Duty certain. From the description and discussion above so researcher wants to examine the Role of Satisfaction and Motivation mediating Culture organization with the performance of lecturers in universities tall private town

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND SUBMISSION OF HYPOTHESES

2.1 Culture Organization

According to Norman (2016) culture organization is something system meaning it has together an organization that makes a difference with organization others. Whereas according to Griffin and Ebbert (2012) culture organization could be interpreted as experience, history, beliefs, and norms being _ characteristic company/organization. A similar definition _ disclosed by Moorhead and Griffin (2012) is that a culture organization set received value _ always right, which helps somebody in the organization to understand which actions are possibly acceptable and which actions are not could receive and values communicated through stories and ways symbolic other.

2.2 Satisfaction Work

Robbins and Timothy (2015) argue that "Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics". Meanwhile, Luthans (2015) defines it as the result of an individual's perception of his work which can be understood in the dimensions of (1) emotional response to work situations ; (2) the dependence on the suitability of the outcome with expectations and (3) its association with various interrelated attitudes towards work. Furthermore, Mangkunegara (2015) stated that job satisfaction is a feeling related to work involving aspects such as wages or salaries received, career development opportunities, relationships with other workers, job placement, type of work, company organizational structure, quality of supervision, age, health conditions, abilities, and education.

2.3. Motivation.

According to Umam (2012: 159). The definition of motivation covered various aspects of the Act or behavior man who can push somebody for behaving or not behaving. However, in terms of following this motivation, it encourages men to act and behave. Meanwhile, according to Robbins (2010), motivation refers to the process by which effort somebody is energized, directed, and sustained going to achieve something purpose. Definition other discovered by Kreitner and Kinicki (2003) stated that motivation is a psychological process that arouses and directs behavior on achievement destination or goal-directed behavior.

According to Uno (2008) in measure, Internal motivation that includes not quite enough he replied in doing a task, carrying out Duty with a clear target, having a destination clear and challenging, there is feedback on the results it works, happy work, always spurred for more

superior from others, and prioritize must achievement _ achieved moment work. Motivation external covers always attempting to fulfill needs in life and work, being happy and praised on work, working with expected incentives, and working with expect noticed by friends and superiors.

2.4. Lecturer Performance

According to Nadeau (2020), lecturer performance is the output of the process carried out by lecturers through work presentations, work implementation, work achievement, work results, and work performance. Supardi (2014) stated that a performance lecturer is an able and successful lecturer in doing work and results achieved _ from their profession. Measurement of teacher performance is needed in educational institutions for determining the enhancement quality of education within the educational institution.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The study uses analysis quantitative with amount sample of as many as 250 university respondents The private sector in Medan City is determined by using Non-Probability Sampling (Sugiono 2015: 84). Research data is analyzed using a structural equation model (SEM) analysis based on partial least squares (PLS). For test influence direct and not direct from variable research used.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

Figure 1. Variable Loading Factor Value Study

Based on Figure 2 shows that the whole variable has Fulfill condition validity with the entire loading factor value indicator value > 0.7. So could conduct testing next.

Construct Reliability Tests

Table 1. Construct Reliability and Validity

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extract...	Copy to Clipb...
X	0.901	0.902	0.920	0.591	
Y	0.894	0.895	0.917	0.612	
Z1	0.878	0.879	0.905	0.577	
Z2	0.888	0.889	0.912	0.598	

The results of the analysis are shown in Table 1 above shows that the AVE value of each latent variable has a value > 0.5 and the value of composite reliability and value Cronbach's alpha

each more latent variable of 0.7 then could conclude indicator variable capable of measure with ok.

Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Table 2. R-Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0.909	0.909
Z1	0.889	0.889
Z2	0.875	0.875

Based on Table 2 above obtained the variable adjusted R-Square value satisfaction work of 0.889 or 88.90% and the rest of 11.1% are influenced by other variables that are not researched in the study. Variable Motivation work the adjusted R-Square value of 0.875 or 87.5% and the rest equal to 12.5% influenced by other variables that are not investigated in research this.

Predictive Relevance (Q2)

The value of Q2 has the same meaning as the coefficient R-Square determination. Big Q squared value (Q2)

0, indicating the model has predictive relevance otherwise if a value (Q2) is less than 0, this shows the model has less predictive relevance in other words where all more Q2 value height, the model is considered could be more suitable with data considerations Q2 value can conduct like following.

$$Q2 = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) (1 - R^2_2) \dots (R_n^2)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (1 - 0.889) (1 - 0.875)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (0.111) (0.125)$$

$$Q2 = 0.986$$

Based on the results the Q2 value of 0.986 so could conclude that the variable in the study this Culture Organization, Satisfaction Work, Motivation work, lecturer performance give authenticity data contribution in the existing structural model by 98.6 %, then the remaining 1.4% is necessary to develop besides from variable study.

Hypothesis Test

Table 3. Influence Direct

Sampel bi... *SAMPEL ... PLS Algori... Bootstrap... PLS Algori...

Path Coefficients

	Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-...		Confidence Intervals		Confidence Intervals Bi
	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
X -> Z1	0.943	0.943	0.009	110.786	0.000
X -> Z2	0.936	0.936	0.007	128.167	0.000
Z1 -> Y	0.472	0.470	0.060	7.851	0.000
Z2 -> Y	0.498	0.499	0.057	8.658	0.000

1. Cultural Influence Organization to Satisfaction work in a manner direct finds that cultural organization takes an effect significant on Satisfaction work. Is the known score significance of Culture Organization of 0.000 more small than 0.05? This means Culture organization the more obeyed in work so will the more increase Satisfaction with work. this result by results of research conducted by Mohammad and Pretty (2017; 15) which states Culture organization take to effect on positive and significant satisfaction work, parallel with that research conducted by Colquitt at, al, Elly Romi (2022), and also in line with research obtained by Ismail (2015; 139) Rifai (2015; 131) which states same that culture organization take effect significant to satisfaction work.

2. Cultural Influence Organization to Motivation work in a manner direct finds that cultural organization takes an effect significant to Motivation work. Is known score significance for Culture Organization of 0.000 more small than 0.05. This means Culture organization the more obeyed in work so will the more increase Motivation work. this result is to the results of research conducted by Elly Romi (2022), and Simamora (2021; 33,) which states Culture organization take an effect positive and significant to Motivation work, parallel with that research conducted by Nawawi at, al (2018;11) found that Culture organization take to effect positive and significant to Motivation work and match with research obtained by Ismail by Syafii at, al (2015;142) Novosesse et.al (2014;438 which states same that culture organization takes effect significant to Motivation work.

3. Effect of Satisfaction work on lecturer performance in a manner direct finds that Satisfaction work takes effect significantly on lecturer performance. Is known score significance Satisfaction work of 0.000 more small than 0.05. This means Satisfaction work the more raise in work so will the more increasing lecturer performs. This result by results on research conducted by Mira hayuningtyas (2017; 39-53) which states Satisfaction work takes an effect

positively and significantly on lecturer performance in line with that research conducted by Elly Sukmanasa. al 2017, Mira labi mandoso at. al 2019., which stated Satisfaction work takes an effect positively and significantly on lecturer performance.

4. Influence of Motivation work on lecturer performance in a manner direct find that Motivation work takes an effect significantly on lecturer performance. Is known score significance Motivation work of 0.000 more small than 0.05. This means Motivation works the more increase in work so will the more increasing lecturer's performance. this result by results on research conducted by Saputra (2020) which states Motivation work take to effect positive and significant on lecturer performance in line with that research conducted _ by Nery (2020), Agustina at. al (2020) state Motivation work takes to effect positive and significant on lecturer performance.

Table 4. Influence Not Direct

The screenshot shows the 'Specific Indirect Effects' table in the SmartPLS software. The table has columns for 'Original Sample (O)', 'Sample Mean (M)', 'Standard Deviation...', 'T Statistic...', and 'P Values'. Two rows are visible: 'X -> Z2 -> Y' with a P Value of 0.000, and 'X -> Z1 -> Y' with a P Value of 0.000.

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation...	T Statistic...	P Values
X -> Z2 -> Y	0.466	0.467	0.054	8.606	0.000
X -> Z1 -> Y	0.445	0.444	0.059	7.563	0.000

5. Cultural Influence organization on lecturer performance through Satisfaction work kindly no direct Satisfaction work takes effect significantly in mediating Culture organization on lecturer performance. this _ could show from score significance of 0.000 small from 0.05. and a big effect of 0.445 or 44.5% can be concluded that Satisfaction work (Z1) donates to culture organization (X) in an increase in Lecturer Performance (Y), namely by 44.5%.

6, Motivation work takes effect significantly in mediating Culture organization on lecturer performance. this _ could show a score significance of 0.000 small than 0.05. and big the effect is 0.446 or 44.6 %. concluded that variable Satisfaction work (Z2) donates to culture organization (X) in an increase in Lecturer Performance (Y), namely by 44.6%

5. Conclusion

Conclusion results study show that cultural organization takes an effect of direct positive and significant satisfaction work and motivation work. Then satisfaction work and motivation work take effect direct positive on lecturer performance. Kindly no direct variable Satisfaction work and motivation work capable mediate Culture organization on lecturer performance College tall Private sector in the city of Medan.

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